

Local journalism in the "Declaración de Santiago + 30"

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Among the agreements of the recent "Declaración de Santiago + 30", adopted at the celebration of World Press Freedom Day in Chile, held on 2 and 4 May 2024, is the need to strengthen local journalism to encourage citizen participation, open government practices, diversity, and plurality.

The Santiago meeting corresponded to the 31st World Press Freedom Day Conference under the theme "press for the planet: journalism in the face of environmental crisis", and coincided with the commemoration of the 1994 "Santiago Declaration", which noted the "commitment to a free press, a vibrant public discourse and the flourishing of democratic societies in Ibero-America and the Caribbean".

This year's declaration explains that changes in communication technologies have enabled new dynamics in information flows, but the commitment to transparency, values, and the promotion of democracy remain the same. However, debates must be held to address emerging concerns such as the sustainability of the media, media and information literacy, the emergence of artificial intelligence and the fight against disinformation, among the issues that will result in how to live together harmoniously on the planet.

In addition to urging states, intergovernmental organizations and technology companies for better journalistic practices and self-regulatory models. The subscribers of the declaration also stress the importance of having accessible and accessible ways for more people to be involved in a different kind of communication, who are not only consumers but also global citizens.